

Business Survey of the German automotive industry

EMPOCI-Questionnaire

Pilot study "Community Acceleration Survey"

May 4, 2026 | English | Open Access | Zenodo Communities: EMPOCI

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Citation

Rogge, K.S., Song, Q. & Mahendiran, S. (2026): Business Survey of the German automotive industry. EMPOCI-Questionnaire. Pilot study "Community Acceleration Survey". University of Sussex, SPRU: Brighton. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20028013>.

Acknowledgements

The questionnaire was developed with support from Hauke Lütkehaus and Joern Hoppmann from the University of Oldenburg (in particular on the mechanisms of phase-out policies) and Nicholas Goedeking from IDOS (in particular on political institutions). Further thanks are due to several colleagues at Fraunhofer ISI for their feedback (notably Aline Scherrer, Josephine Tröger, Patrick Plötz and Till Gnann), as well as to Jan Fridtjof Otto from Utrecht University.

Funding

This questionnaire was developed as part of the EMPOCI project, which was funded by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 852730).

EMPOCI business survey in the German automotive industry

Target Respondents

Management Executives (e.g. Managing Director(s), Executive Board, Strategic Leadership Team, potentially the head of R&D) with expertise in innovation, production and policy, and, if applicable, with insights into the ongoing transformation of the automotive industry towards electro-mobility

Topic

This survey addresses the transformation of the German automotive industry, with a particular focus on maintaining its competitiveness in a climate-neutral future.

This questionnaire collects information about business activities in the German automotive industry.

In doing so, it distinguishes these activities into two technological domains:

- those related to vehicles with internal combustion engines (short: 'ICEV') and
- those related to electric vehicles (short: 'EV').

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Legend & Notes on CATI/CAWI implementation

{INT: Text} = INT in red: Explanation for interviewer, if in {} only to be read out when asked. INT in green: The explanations are visible to online participants in green, including such in {}. They start with: 'Note: xxx, i.e. followed by the text', which here in the questionnaire is red (the colour for the CATI interviewers, except when there are only partial texts for CAWI, then that is green, too.

{Alternative: Do not know [98], Prefer not to say [99]} → In CAWI, these response option are shown at the bottom in a light grey list, with the following text: „ Cannot answer. / Prefer not to answer.“

CAWI error message text: On top: “There are unanswered questions on this page.” Nearby the questions: “Please answer all questions.”

CAWI: Instructions on the scales are not written, rather the scale simply appears in the screen, with the first (1) and last item (6) being explained with a note.

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I: INTRODUCTION: general information about your enterprise

1.1 {organisation} Is your enterprise part of an enterprise group?

{INT: Enterprise group = corporate group or group of companies under common control}

Yes [1] → If “1.1 = Yes [1]”, ask to specify:

1.1.a {HQ} In which country is the headquarter located?

In Germany [1] → If [1], ask to specify:

1.1.a_1 {group} Are all enterprises within the enterprise group located in Germany?

Yes [1]

No, also group enterprises abroad [2]

Abroad [2] → If [2], ask to specify:

1.1.a_2 {country} In which country is the headquarter of your enterprise group?

_____ [open text field for country]

No [2]

{Filter: If “1.1 = Yes [1]”, follow up with this statement for enterprises that are part of an enterprise group.}

Please answer all further questions exclusively based on the activities of your own enterprise at its location in Germany.

Exclude the activities of all subsidiaries or parent enterprises.

{Filter: If “1.1 = No [2]”, follow up with the following statement.}

Please answer all further questions exclusively based on the activities of your enterprise at its location in Germany.

1.2 {German HQ} In which federal state in Germany is your enterprise’s German headquarter located?

[1] Schleswig-Holstein

[2] Hamburg

[3] Lower Saxony

[4] Bremen

[5] North Rhine-Westphalia

[6] Hesse

[7] Rhineland-Palatinate

[8] Baden-Württemberg

[9] Bavaria

[10] Saarland

[11] Berlin

[12] Brandenburg

[13] Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania

[14] Saxony

[15] Saxony-Anhalt

[16] Thuringia

[98] Cannot answer

1.3 {supply chain position} What is your enterprise’s main position in the automotive industry: OEM or supplier? Or are you active in the wider automotive eco-system?

{INT: Multiple answers possible. Please select all applicable positions.}

{Alternatively: Do not know [98]}. → If no assignment at the higher level is possible: **Unfortunately, you do not belong to the target group for this study.** {INT: End of survey.}

1.3.a OEM [1] {INT: Original equipment manufacturer = vehicle manufacturer}

→ If 1.3.a selected:

Please specify for which of the following?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 1.3.a_1 Passenger cars [1]
- 1.3.a_2 Vans [2] {INT: Light commercial vehicles (≤3.5t).}
- 1.3.a_3 Trucks and lorries [3] {INT: Medium and heavy duty commercial vehicles (≥ 3.5t).}
- 1.3.a_4 Buses and coaches [4] {INT: More than 8 seats.}
- 1.3.a_5 Others [5] → If selected, please specify: 1.3.a_5_X: _____

{Filter} Every enterprise that selects 1.3.a proceeds (with 1.3.a_1–4), except if only 1.3.a_5 is selected and not qualified through selection of 1.3.b or 1.3.c}

→ **Unfortunately, you are not part of this study’s target group.**

{INT: End of survey.}

1.3.b Supplier [1]

→ If 1.3.b selected:

Please specify for which of the following?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 1.3.b_1 Powertrain [1] {INT: Comprises engine (internal combustion or electric motor), transmission, driveshafts, axles, clutch.}
- 1.3.b_2 Battery [2]
- 1.3.b_3 Chassis [3]
- 1.3.b_4 Interior [4]
- 1.3.b_5 Exterior [5]
- 1.3.b_6 Electrics [6] {INT: ‘Electrics’ refers to systems responsible for generating, storing, and distributing electrical power throughout the vehicle.}
- 1.3.b_7 Electronics [7] {INT: ‘Electronics’ involves systems that control and manage vehicle functions using components like microcontrollers, sensors, and software.}
- 1.3.b_8 Consumables [8]

1.3.c Wider automotive eco-system [1]

→ If 1.3.c selected:

Please specify for which of the following?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 1.3.c_1 Production equipment manufacturer [1]
- 1.3.c_2 Charging equipment manufacturer [2]
- 1.3.c_3 Digital platform technology provider [3]
- 1.3.c_4 Infrastructure service provider [4]

- 1.3.c_5 Others [5] → If selected, please specify: 1.3.c_5_X: _____

→ If only 1.3.c_4 and/or 1.3.c_5 selected, and NOT 1.3.a_1-4 and/or 1.3.b:

→ **Unfortunately, you are not part of this study's target group.**

{INT: End of survey.}

1.3.d Others [1] → If 1.3.d selected, please specify 1.3.d_X: _____

→ If only 1.3.d selected, and NOT 1.3.a_1-4 and/or 1.3.b and/or 1.3.c.1-3:

→ **Unfortunately, you are not part of this study's target group.**

{INT: End of survey.}

{Filter: Only ask those that selected: „1.3.b = [1] supplier“}

1.4 {supplier tier} As a supplier, which positions do you hold in the automotive supply chain?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.}

{INT: There are suppliers who sell their products either directly to OEMs or also to Tier-1 suppliers; they are therefore both Tier-1 and Tier-2 suppliers..}

Tier one [1] {INT: First-tier suppliers are enterprises that supply directly to the automakers, meaning they work directly with the OEMs (=vehicle manufacturers) and deliver complete systems or assemblies. Typical examples: Bosch, Continental, ZF.}

Tier two [2] {INT: Suppliers of the second tier typically provide parts or components to Tier-1 suppliers.}

Tier three [3] {INT: Third-tier suppliers provide raw materials or components to Tier-2 suppliers. Examples: steel, aluminium, chemicals.}

Do not know [98] {INT: If „do not know“, please read out: **Tier-1- and Tier-2-suppliers typically require certain certifications, e.g. IATF 16949 (Automotive Quality Management System) or VDA 6.1 (Quality System Audit Standard – Automotive) – does your enterprise have these?** If yes, please also select Tier 1 and/or 2. {i.e. leave ‘don’t know’ if the respondent still does not know.}

If only [Tier three] oder [Do not know] is selected, and NOT 1.3.a_1-4 and/or 1.3.c_1-3:

→ **Unfortunately, you are not part of this study's target group.** {INT: End of survey.}

{Filter: Only ask those that selected: „1.3.b = [1]“ (supplier) or „1.3.c_1 = [1]“ or „1.3.c_2 = [1]“ or „1.3.c_3 = [1]“ (enterprises from the wider automotive eco-system).}

1.5 {suppliers for OEMs} For which of the following automotive products does your enterprise supply goods or services (including equipment)?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 1.5.a Passenger cars [1]
- 1.5.b Vans [2] {INT: Light commercial vehicles ($\leq 3.5t$).}
- 1.5.c Trucks and lorries [3] {INT: Medium and heavy duty commercial vehicles ($\geq 3.5t$).}
- 1.5.d Buses and coaches [4] {INT: More than 8 seats.}
- 1.5.e Others [5] → If selected, please specify: 1.5.e_X: _____

If only 1.5.e selected, and NOT 1.3.a_1-4 or/and 1.3.c.1-3:

→ **Unfortunately, you are not part of this study's target group.** {INT: End of survey.}

1.6 {technological trajectory} To which technological domains do these goods or services relate to?

{INT: If you cannot clearly distinguish between ICEV and EV domains, select both options.}

Goods or services related to...

1.6.a {traditional} ...internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs)

{INT: This includes all vehicles whose engine is powered by burning petrol, oil, or other fuels.}

{INT: Other fuels in ICEVs can include biofuels and synthetic fuels (incl. e-fuels), but also hydrogen. Full hybrids are also part of ICEVs. In contrast, plug-in hybrids (PHEV) belong to EVs.}

Yes [1] / No [2] {Alternatively: Do not know [98]}

→ If “1.6.a = Yes [1]”, please specify: **Since which year or for how many years have you been offering goods or services for ICEVs?**
{Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

1.6.a_X Specify year: ____ [YYYY] {INT: An estimate is also possible.}

{or}

1.6.a_j For how many years? ____ [yyyy] {INT: An estimate is also possible.}

1.6.b {electrification} ...electric vehicles (EVs)

{INT: This includes battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in hybrid vehicles (PHEVs), as well as fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs).}

{INT: Note that Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) are considered in the technological domain of EVs, where hydrogen is used.}

Yes [1] / No [2]. {Alternatively: Do not know [98]}

{INT: → If „1.6.b = No [2]”, please follow up:

Are these goods or services relevant for fuel cell electric vehicles?

Yes [1] → If “yes”, please explain: “We consider these as electric vehicles.”

{Change answer in 1.6.b to Yes [1], and tick 1.6.b_2 FCEV with Yes [1].}

- No [2]
- Do not know [98]

→ If 1.6.b = “Yes [1]”, please specify:

1.6.b_X: To which of the following types do these goods or services in the EV domain belong?

{Alternatively: Do not know [98]}

1.6.b_X_1 {BEV} Battery Electric Vehicles

{INT: also known as all-electric or 100% electric vehicle, means an electric vehicle that exclusively runs on the electric motor, with no secondary source of propulsion. }

Yes [1] / No [2] *{Alternatively: Do not know [98]}*

1.6.b_X_2 {FCEV} Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles

{INT: uses a fuel cell to power its on-board electric motor, generally using oxygen from the air and compressed hydrogen. A fuel cell electric vehicle that is fueled with hydrogen emits only water and heat. }

Yes [1] / No [2] *{Alternatively: Do not know [98]}*

1.6.b_X_3 {PHEV} Plug-in hybrid Vehicles

{INT: electric vehicle constituted by a conventional combustion engine combined with an electric propulsion system, which can be recharged from an external electric power source. }

Yes [1] / No [2] *{Alternatively: Do not know [98]}*

→ If 1.6.b = “Yes [1]”, please specify: **1.6.b_X: Since which year or for how many years have you been offering goods or services for EVs?**

{Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

1.6.b_X Specify year: ____ [YYYY] *{INT: An estimate is also possible. }*

{or}

1.6.b_j For how many years? ____ [yyyy] *{INT: An estimate is also possible. }*

II: POLICY FRAMEWORK CONDITIONS: policy mix in Germany and Europe

The following questions refer to the policy framework conditions relevant for the ongoing transformation of the automotive industry in Germany.

2.1 {policy objectives} From your enterprise’s perspective, please indicate how important the following policy objectives are for the transformation of the German automotive industry.

Please use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means “not at all important” and 6 means “very important”. You can use the numbers in between to differentiate your assessment in steps. [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

2.1.a {IP} **Competitiveness.**

2.1.b {CP} **Decarbonisation.**

2.1.c {EP} **Energy security.**

2.1.d {CE} **Circular economy.**

2.2 {characteristics} Considering all current policies in Germany, to which extent do you agree with the following statements?

Please evaluate the statements from your enterprise’s perspective using a scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. [1:6] {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

The transformation of the German automotive industry...

2.2.a {3rd level consistency} ... will be achieved with the existing policies.

2.2.b {2nd level consistency} ... is impeded by tensions between existing policies.

2.2.c {comprehensiveness} ... requires the introduction of important flanking policies.

2.3 {instrument mix} For the year 2024, please say how much you think the German and European policies in the following policy areas have supported the transformation of the German automotive industry from your enterprise's perspective.

Please use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means "not supported at all" and 6 means "fully supported". You can use the numbers in between to differentiate your assessment in steps. [1:6] {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

2.3.a {technology push} Policy support for research, development and demonstration related to the technological domain...

2.3.a_1 {TP_ICEV} ...ICEVs (e.g. for e-fuels)

2.3.a_2 {TP_EV} ... EVs (e.g. for batteries)

2.3.b {demand pull} Policy support stimulating market demand for...

2.3.b_1 {DP_ICEV} ... ICEVs (e.g. preferential tax treatment)

2.3.b_2 {DP_EV} ...EVs (e.g. purchasing subsidies)

2.3.c {systemic policies} Policy support for the availability of...

2.3.c_1 {SYS_electricity} ... cheap and clean electricity (e.g. exemptions from surcharges)

2.3.c_2 {SYS_charging} ... electric charging infrastructure (e.g. funding programs)

And how much have the following policies supported the transformation of the German automotive industry in 2024?

Please evaluate this again from 1 to 6, with 1 meaning "not support at all" and 6 meaning "fully supported". You can again use the numbers in between to differentiate your assessment in steps. [1:6]

2.3.d {industrial policy} Policy support for domestic production by...

2.3.d_1 {IP_finance} ... providing finance for and/or de-risking of investments
(e.g. public loans)

2.3.d_2 {IP_skills} ... ensuring the availability of a skilled workforce (e.g. retraining)

2.3.d_3 {IP_regional} ... strengthening regional clusters (e.g. transformation networks)

2.3.e {phase-out policies} Policies encouraging decarbonisation activities by...

2.3.e_1 {PO_producers} ... producers (e.g. CO₂ emissions fleet standards)

2.3.e_2 {PO_consumers} ...consumers (e.g. CO₂ price)

2.3.f {environmental policies} Policies aimed at reducing environmental impacts from ...

2.3.f_1 {ENV_CO₂} ... air pollution (e.g. EURO 7 standards)

2.3.f_2 {ENV_CE} ... resource use (e.g. circular economy provisions)

In 2023, the European Commission has adopted a 100% zero emission sales standard for new passenger cars and light commercial vehicles for 2035.

2.4 {phase out/in strategy} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements regarding the EU’s so called “ban on internal combustion engines” for new vehicles by 2035 from your enterprise’s perspective.

*Please answer again using a scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. [1:6]
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}*

This policy target is ...

2.4.a {ambition} ...very ambitious.

2.4.b {guidance} ...providing planning security.

2.4.c {1st level consistency IP} ... well aligned with the competitiveness policy objective.

2.4.d {1st level consistency CP} ...well aligned with the decarbonisation policy objective.

2.4.e {credibility} ... likely to be relaxed.

2.5 {phase out/in strategy - impact} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements on how this policy change impacted your automotive business strategy.

*Please answer using a scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. [1:6]
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}*

The adoption of the so called “ICEV ban”...

2.5.a {attention} ... increased our willingness to allocate resources to zero-emission technologies.

2.5.b {exclusion} ... reduced the risk associated with a strategy focused on EVs.

2.5.c {forecast} ... supported the transformation of our enterprise with a clear temporal reference point.

2.5.d {coordination} ... facilitated coordination between our enterprise’s transformation and the automotive eco-system.

We now turn to the nature of policy making processes. Again, please answer all questions from the perspective of your enterprise, focusing on the last year 2024.

2.6 {political institutions} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements on the institutional framework conditions in Germany for the year 2024.

Please use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. You can use the numbers in between to differentiate your assessment in steps. [1:6] {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 2.6.a {rules - constitution} The 2021 climate ruling by the Federal Constitutional Court, based on the Basic Law, required the German federal government to pursue ambitious climate policies.
- 2.6.b {rules - mandate} The sector-specific targets in the German Climate Protection Act required the responsible ministries to introduce ambitious policies to meet those targets.
- 2.6.c {process - budget} The revenues from carbon pricing provided a reliable source of income for the financial support of climate-neutral investments.
- 2.6.d {process - bureaucracy} The bureaucratic hassles involved in obtaining public permits for infrastructure investments were acceptable.
- 2.6.e {sector} The electricity market design provided clear incentives for climate investments.

2.7 {coherence} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements on the policy making processes related to the transformation of the German automotive industry in the year 2024.

Please answer again using the same scale from 1 to 6, and again from your enterprise’s perspective. [1:6]

{INT: 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”}
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 2.7.a {coherence - informational} There was a continuous exchange of information between policymakers and industry.
- 2.7.b {coherence - procedural} The search for solutions to problems took place in transparent procedures.
- 2.7.c {coherence - political} The government effectively balanced the interests of all relevant players.
- 2.7.d {coherence - coordination} The relevant national ministries have coordinated effectively.

2.8 {multi-level governance} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements on policy actors for the year 2024.

Please again use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. You can use the numbers in between to differentiate your assessment in steps. [1:6] {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

Concerning the transformation of the German automotive industry, there was strong support from the following governance levels:

- 2.8.a {EU} The European Commission
- 2.8.b {BR} Germany’s national government
- 2.8.c {BL} The State government of {BL} {insert answer from 1.2 for HQ of enterprise}
- 2.8.d {LO} The local government authorities in {BL} {insert answer from 1.2 for HQ of enterprise}

2.8.e {vertical coordination} Policymakers across these different governance levels coordinated effectively in supporting the transformation of the German automotive industry.

2.9 {credibility development} All in all: How strong do you think the political will of the German national government was to support the transformation of the automotive industry in Germany at the following points in time?

For each point in time, we mention a specific event to help you remember your enterprise’s perspective back then.

Please assess the strength of the political will from your enterprise’s perspective using a scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “not strong at all” and 6 means “very strong”. [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

Strength of political will ...

- 2.9.a ... in December 2021: Coalition agreement of the traffic light government
- 2.9.b ... in March 2022: Tesla opens its Gigafactory Berlin-Brandenburg
- 2.9.c ... in November 2023: Constitutional budget crisis leading to cuts in e-mobility funding
- 2.9.d ... in April 2024: Reform of the climate protection law abandoning binding sector targets
- 2.9.e ... in April 2025: Coalition agreement of the political parties CDU/CSU and SPD
- 2.9.f ... today: How strong do you expect the new government’s political will to be to support the transformation of the German automotive industry?

→ 2.9.f_1 {uncertainty}: **How certain are you about your expectation for today?**

Please answer on a scale from 1-6, 1 means “not certain at all”, 6 “very certain”.

III: BUSINESS ACTIVITIES: transformation, innovation, production, global links

We now turn to the business activities of your enterprise in Germany.

3.1 {innovation-production screening} During the past three years 2022 to 2024, did your enterprise undertake any innovation activities or production capacity adjustments?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

3.1.a {innovation} Innovation activities: Yes [1] / No [2]

{INT: {If ‘no’ or upon request, please read aloud.} Any actions undertaken with the intention to develop innovations, such as new or significantly improved products, processes or services. These innovation activities can result in an innovation, be ongoing, postponed or abandoned.}

3.1.b {production} Production capacity changes: Yes [1] / No [2]

{INT: {If ‘no’ or upon request, please read aloud.} Any actions undertaken to adjust the scale and/or scope of manufacturing of goods and services (e.g. replacing, expanding, decreasing, relocating), including changes in buildings, machinery, equipment and IT.}

III. A: Transformation towards e-mobility

3.2 {transformation status} Overall, how far advanced is your enterprise in orienting its automotive business towards e-mobility.

Please use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means “not started” and 6 “fully oriented towards e-mobility”.

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99].}

{Filter: Ask all that answered >1 for 3.23: “3.2 = [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], do not know [98], no response [99].}

3.3 {transformation areas} And when looking at your enterprise’s efforts to orient its automotive business towards e-mobility, please indicate how active your enterprise has been in this regard in the following areas in the year 2024.

Please use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means “no activities” and 6 means “very high activities”.
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99].}

Orientation towards e-mobility regarding our ...

- 3.3_1 **R&D activities** (e.g. e-mobility-related R&D)
- 3.3_2 **Intellectual property rights** (e.g., e-mobility-related patenting, trademarking or copyrights)
- 3.3_3 **Product portfolio** (e.g. new e-mobility-related products or services)
- 3.3_4 **Marketing strategy** (e.g. e-mobility-focused advertisement)
- 3.3_5 **Production capacity and manufacturing process** (e.g. repurposing facilities for EV demands)
- 3.3_6 **Digitalisation** (e.g. interoperability, cybersecurity, AI, automation for e-mobility)
- 3.3_7 **Organizational structure** (e.g. creation or re-organization of e-mobility-related business units)
- 3.3_8 **Human resource management** (e.g. hiring e-mobility experts or re-training employees)
- 3.3_9 **Supply chain** (e.g. shifts in global sourcing and logistics for e-mobility)
- 3.3_10 **Mergers, acquisitions and joint ventures** (e.g. new e-mobility-related R&D partnerships)
- 3.3_11 **Public Relations (PR)** (e.g. media efforts and public campaigns regarding e-mobility activities)
- 3.3_12 **Political engagement** (e.g. lobbying for policy support for the transformation to e-mobility)
- 3.3_13 **Others** *{INT: If not applicable, please select [1] {no activity}.}*
If [2-6] selected: **If others, please specify?** 3.3.13_X _____ *{INT: Record open response.}*
{Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99].}

{Filter: Ask all that answered “3.2 = [2], [3], [4], [5], [6]”}.

3.4A {determinants - transformers} During the past three years 2022 to 2024, how important were the following factors for orienting your enterprise’s business activities towards e-mobility.

Please use a scale from 1 to 6, where 1 means “not at all important” and 6 “very important”.

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99].}

3.4A_1 {market_domestic} Shifts in domestic market demand towards EVs (in Germany and EU)

3.4A_2 {market_global} Shifts in global market demand towards EVs (e.g. in China)

3.4A_3 {sector_mimicry} Benchmarking with domestic competitors {in Germany and EU}

3.4A_4 {sector_competition} Catch up with global innovation leaders (e.g., Tesla, CATL)

3.4A_5 {policy_domestic} Domestic industrial and climate policies for e-mobility (in Germany and Europe)

3.4A_6 {policy_international} Foreign industrial and climate policies for e-mobility

3.4A_7 {legitimacy_external} Societal support for the transition to e-mobility (in Germany and Europe)

3.4A_8 {legitimacy_internal} Transformative leadership within your enterprise

3.4A_9 {others} Other factors → If between 2 and 6, please ask to specify:

Which factors does this concern? 3.4.A_9_X: _____ {INT: Record open response.}

{Filter: Only ask if “3.2 = [1]” (Those that did not start orientation towards e-mobility) or „3.2 = [98] do not know or [99] no response“}.

3.4B {determinants - non-transformers} Please tell us the most important reasons for not orienting your enterprise’s business activities towards e-mobility during the past three years 2022 to 2024.

{INT: Let the respondent answer freely and write it down. If in doubt, ask for the 2-3 most important factors.}

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

III. B: Innovation activities of your enterprise

{Filter: Only read out to respondents with “3.1.a = Yes [1]”.} {Note: Those with “No” [2] or Don’t Know [-99] at “3.1.a” get separate questions (see grey shading).}

We will now ask a few questions about the innovation activities of your enterprise in Germany.

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.1.a = Yes [1]”.}

3.5 {innovation trajectory} During the past three years 2022 to 2024, did your enterprise undertake any innovation activities related to the automotive industry?

{INT: Examples of business innovation activities include:

- research and experimental development (R&D) activities
- engineering, design and other creative work activities
- marketing and brand equity activities
- intellectual property (IP) related activities
- employee training activities
- software development and database activities
- activities related to the acquisition or lease of tangible assets
- innovation management activities. }

Yes [1] / No [2] {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

If “3.5 = Yes [1]”, then continue: **Were these innovation activities related to ...**

3.5.a ...ICEVs? Yes [1] / No [2]

3.5.b ...EVs? Yes [1] / No [2]

3.5.c ...Digitalisation? Yes [1] / No [2]

{INT: Digitalization within the company and its products. On the product side, we are referring to, among other things, the transition towards software-enabled, connected and autonomous vehicles, with new applications such as automated and autonomous driving, bi-directional and smart charging, or communication and infotainment. }

{INT: Do not read aloud! The enterprise may be unable to distinguish between the ICEV and EV domains (e.g. if components are supplied independently of the drive technology and no market distinction is made between the two domains).

3.5.x Distinction not possible [1]

The following questions will focus on innovations related to the technological domains of ICEVs and/or EVs. Please include any digital innovations within these areas.

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = Yes [1]”.}

3.6 {innovation collaborators} Please specify the actor type of your innovation collaborators.

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- [1] No collaborators → If “3.6.a = [1]”, skip to next question, otherwise continue.
- [2] Other enterprises
- [3] Universities and/or research institutes
- [4] Civil society actors (e.g. user associations, NGOs, think tanks)
- [5] Policy actors (e.g. public investment banks, public advisors, regulators)
- [6] Others

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.6 = [2] Other enterprises”.

3.6_X {sector collaborators} In which of the following sectors are these enterprises based?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- [1] Automotive
- [2] Electricity / Energy
- [3] ICT (Information and Communication Technology)
- [4] Others

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = Yes [1]”.}

3.7 {innovation expenditure 2024 - automotive} Please specify your enterprise’s automotive innovation expenditure in 2024. Please round up to the nearest thousand.

{INT: Read aloud if necessary: Innovation expenditures are the economic costs of your company’s innovation activities. Expenditures may relate to internal innovation activities (e.g., R&D personnel costs) and external innovation activities (e.g., commissioning R&D projects to third parties). If unsure, please estimate.}

{Alternatively: More than one billion € [999997]; do not know [999998]; prefer not to say [999999]}

Automotive innovation expenditures approximately ____ thousand €

{Filter: Only ask if 3.7 do not know, or prefer not to say.}

{INT: Alternatively, ask at least for the range within which their enterprise’s automotive innovation expenditure falls.}

3.7_X Could you instead please say which of the following categories your automotive innovation expenditures fell into in 2024? *{Alternatively: Do not know [98], No response [99]}*

- [1] under 5 million €
- [2] 5-10 million €
- [3] 10-15 million €
- [4] 15-20 million €
- [5] 20-30 million €
- [6] over 30 million €

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.5.x = [1]”.

3.5 {innovation expenditure 2024 - TECH} In 2024, what percentage of your enterprise’s automotive innovation expenditure has been related to these technological domains?

{INT: Two decimal places possible. If unsure, please have the respondent provide an estimate. Two decimal places are possible. The period functions as the decimal separator.}

{Alternatively: do not know [999998]; prefer not to say [999999]}

Share related to...

3.5.a ...ICEVs {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5.a = Yes [1]”.}

Ca. ____ % *{INT: Each can be up to 100%.}*

3.5.b ...EVs {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5.b = Yes [1]”.}

Ca. ____ % *{INT: Each can be up to 100%.}*

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5.a = Yes [1]” AND NOT “3.5.x = [1]”.}

3.9.A_1 {innovation expenditure - speed - ICEV - past} How have your enterprise’s automotive innovation expenditures related to ICEVs changed in 2024 compared to 2023?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increased → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.A_1_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2024, but none in 2023.}
- [2] Remained approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decreased [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.A_1_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No innovation expenditure in 2023 and 2024

3.9.A_2 {innovation expenditure - speed - ICEV - future} How do you expect your enterprise’s innovation expenditures related to ICEV to change in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increase → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.A_2_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2025, but none in 2024.}
- [2] Remain approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decrease [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.A_2_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No innovation expenditure in 2024 and 2025 (expected)

{Filter: Only for respondents with “3.5.a = Yes [1]” (ICE innovation) AND “3.5.b = No [2]” (EV innovation). Skip for respondents with “3.5.x = [1]”.}

3.9.A_X Do you expect to undertake innovation expenditure related to EV in 2025?

- Yes [1] / No [2]

{Filter: Only for respondents with “3.5.b = Yes [1]” AND NOT “3.5.x = [1]”.}

3.9.B_1 {innovation expenditure - speed - EV - past} How have your enterprise’s innovation expenditures related to EVs changed in 2024 compared to 2023?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increased → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.B_1_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2024, but none in 2023.}
- [2] Remained approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decreased [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.B_1_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No innovation expenditure in 2023 and 2024

3.9.B_2 {innovation expenditure - speed - EV - future} And how do you expect these innovation expenditures related to EVs to change in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increase → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.B_2_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2025, but none in 2024.}
- [2] Remain approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decrease [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.B_2_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No innovation expenditure in 2024 and 2025 (expected)

{Filter: Only for respondents with “3.5.b = Yes [1]” (ICE innovation) AND “3.5.a = No [2]” (EV innovation). Skip for respondents with “3.5.x = [1]”.}

3.9.B_X Do you expect to undertake innovation expenditure related to ICEV in 2025?

- Yes [1] / No [2]

{Filter: Only for respondents with “3.5.x = [1]”.}

3.9.X_1 {innovation expenditure - speed - automotive - past} How have your enterprise’s automotive innovation expenditures changed in 2024 compared to 2023?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increased → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.B_1_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2024, but none in 2023.}
- [2] Remained approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decreased [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.B_1_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No innovation expenditure in 2023 and 2024

3.9.X_2 {innovation expenditure - speed - automotive} And how do you expect your innovation expenditure to change in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increase → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.X_2_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2025, but none in 2024.}
- [2] Remain approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decrease [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.9.X_2_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No innovation expenditure in 2024 and 2025 (expected)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = Yes [1]”.}

3.10 {innovation funding} During the past three years 2022 to 2024, did your enterprise receive any public financial R&D or innovation support for your innovation activities related to the following technological domains?

Please include any public innovation support from Germany and the EU.

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

{INT: R&D (research and development) and innovation support includes financial support of R&D/innovation projects by public bodies, such as grants, loans, subsidies, shareholding or loan guarantees. Standard payments for public contracts do not count as public support. Please also include support from authorized institutions, such as project management agencies or development banks.}

3.10.a ICEVs: Yes [1] / No [2] {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5.a = Yes [1]”.}

3.10.b EVs: Yes [1] / No [2] {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5.b = Yes [1]”.}

3.10.x Automotive: Yes [1] / No [2] {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5.x = Yes [1]”.}

{Filter: Only to respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR Do not know [98] OR Prefer not to say [99]” (i.e. those not innovating in the past 3 years, or did not know about or did not want to share the past innovation activities).}

We will ask some questions about possible future innovation activities in your enterprise in Germany.

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR “Do not know [98] OR Prefer not to say [99]”}.

3.11 {new innovators 2025} Does your enterprise plan to undertake any innovation activities in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

Yes [1] / No [2]

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR “Do not know [98] OR Prefer not to say [99] AND “3.11 = Yes [1]”}.

3.12 {new innovators 2025 - TECH} To which of the following technological domains are these innovation activities in 2025 related to?

{INT: Multiple answers possible.} {Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

Innovation activities related to...

[1] ... ICEVs

[2] ... EVs

[3] ... **Digitalisation** {INT: Digitalization within the company and its products. On the product side, we are referring to, among other things, the transition towards software-enabled, connected and autonomous vehicles, with new applications such as automated and autonomous driving, bi-directional and smart charging, or communication and infotainment.}

The following questions focus on innovations related to the technological domains of ICEVs and/or EVs. Please include any digital innovations within these areas.

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.2 = No [2] OR Don’t Know [-99]” and “3.8 = Yes [1]”.}

3.13 {innovation expenditure - new 2025} What **automotive innovation expenditure** do you expect for your enterprise **in 2025** related to the following technological domains? Please round up to the nearest thousand.

{INT: If unsure, please have the respondent provide an estimate. Two decimal places are possible. The period functions as the decimal separator. Do not know [999998]; prefer not to say [999999]}

Innovation expenditures related to...

3.13.a ...ICEVs: approx. __ thousand € {Filter: only if “3.12.a = [1]”}

3.13.b ...EVs: approx. __ thousand € {Filter: only if “3.12.b = [1].”}

{INT: If an enterprise cannot distinguish between the ICEV and EV domains (e.g. if components are supplied independently of the drive technology and no market distinction is made between the two domains), then please ask for the total automotive innovation expenditures.}

3.13.x ... Automotive: approx. __ thousand € *{INT: Only if distinction not possible.}*

III. C: Changes in production capacity of your enterprise

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.1.b = Yes [1]”.}

{Note: Those with “No [2] at 3.1.b” get separate questions (see grey shading).}

We will now ask some questions about the changes in production capacity in your enterprise in Germany.

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.1.b = Yes [1]”}

3.14 {production trajectory} During the past three years 2022 to 2024, did your enterprise undertake any changes in your production capacity related to the automotive industry?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

Yes [1] / No [2]

If “3.14 = Yes [1]”, then continue: **Were these changes in production capacity related to...**

3.14.a ...ICEVs? Yes [1] / No [2]

3.14.b ... EVs? Yes [1] / No [2]

{INT: Do not read aloud! The enterprise may be unable to distinguish between the ICEV and EV domains (e.g. if components are supplied independently of the drive technology and no market distinction is made between the two domains).}

3.14.x Distinction not possible [1]

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.a = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.15.A {capacity adjustments - ICEV} During the past three years, what type of production capacity adjustments did your enterprise undertake related to the technological domain ‘ICEV’?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- **3.15.A_1 Modernizing production capacity** (e.g. upgrading or renewing existing ICEV-related buildings, machinery, equipment or IT) [1]
- **3.15.A_2 Expanding production capacity** [1] → If selected, please specify:
Were some of these expansions connected to...
 - **3.15.A_2_1 ... adding new facilities for ICEVs?** [1]
 - **3.15.A_2_2 ...relocating ICEV-related facilities into Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify country of origin: **3.15.A_2_2_X:** ____)
- **3.15.A_3 Reducing production capacity** (e.g. repurposing or closing ICEV-related facilities) [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these reductions connected to...
 - **3.15.A_3_1 ... repurposing facilities?** (e.g. shifting assets and equipment away from ICEV-related production) [1]
(If yes, please specify new purpose(s): **3.15.A_3_1_X:** ____)
 - **3.15.A_3_2 ... relocating ICEV-related facilities out of Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify destination country **3.15.A_3_2_X:** ____)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.b = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]}.

3.15.B {capacity adjustments - EV} During the past three years, what type of production capacity adjustments did your enterprise undertake related to the technological domain ‘EV’?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- **3.15.B_1 Modernizing production capacity** (e.g. upgrading or renewing existing EV-related buildings, machinery, equipment or IT) [1]
- **3.15.B_2 Expanding production capacity** [1] → If selected, please specify:
Were some of these expansions connected to...
 - **3.15.B_2_1 ... adding new facilities for EVs ?** [1]
 - **3.15.B_2_2 ... relocating EV-related facilities into Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify country of origin **3.15.B_2_2_X:** _____)
- **3.15.B_3 Reducing production capacity** (e.g. repurposing or closing EV-related facilities) [1] → If selected, please specify:
Were some of these reductions connected to...
 - **3.15.B_3_1 ... repurposing facilities?** (e.g. shifting assets and equipment away from EV-related production) [1]
(If yes, please specify new purpose(s): **3.15.B_3_1_X:** _____)
 - **3.15.B_3_2 ... relocating EV-related facilities out of Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify destination country: **3.15.B_3_2_X:** _____)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.15.X {capacity adjustments - automotive} During the past three years, what type of production capacity adjustments did your enterprise undertake related to the automotive domain?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- **3.15.X_1 Modernizing production capacity** (e.g. upgrading or renewing existing buildings, machinery, equipment or IT related to the automotive domain) [1]
- **3.15.X_2 Expanding production capacity** [1] → If selected, please specify:

Were some of these expansions connected to...

- **3.15.X_2_1 ... adding new automotive facilities?** [1]
- **3.15.X_2_2 ... relocating automotive facilities into Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify country of origin **3.15.X_2_2_X**: _____)

- **3.15.X_3 Reducing production capacity** (e.g. repurposing or closing automotive facilities) [1] → If selected, please specify:

Were some of these reductions connected to...

- **3.15.X_3_1 ... repurposing automotive facilities?** (e.g. shifting assets and equipment away from automotive in the current portfolio) [1]
(If yes, please specify new purpose(s): **3.15.B_3_1_X**: _____)
- **3.15.X_3_2 ... relocating automotive facilities out of Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify destination country: **3.15.X_3_2_X**: _____)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR Don’t know [98]” AND “3.14 = Yes [1]”.}

3.16 {capacity investment - present} Please estimate the production capacity investments for the automotive business of your enterprise in 2024. Round your answer up to the nearest thousand.

{INT: Any capital expenditures (capex) undertaken by your enterprise to adjust the scale and/or scope of manufacturing of goods and services, including for changes in buildings, machinery, equipment and IT.}

{INT: If unsure, please have the respondent provide an estimate.}

{Alternatively: More than 1 billion € [999997]; do not know [999998]; prefer not to say [999999].}

3.16.a Overall automotive production capacity investments in 2024:

Approximately ____ thousand €

Of this, what percentage has gone into the following technological domains?

{Filter: Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.16.b ICEVs: ca. __ % {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.a = Yes [1]”.}

3.16.c EVs: ca. __ % {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.b = Yes [1]”.}

{INT: If very difficult to separate, please collect the answers to this and the following questions as estimates. / If unsure, please provide an estimate.}

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR Don’t know [98] OR No response” AND “3.14.a = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.17.A_1 {capacity investment - speed - ICEV - past} How have your enterprise’s automotive production capacity investments related to ICEVs changed in 2024 compared to 2023?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increased → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.A_1_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there were investments in 2024, but none in 2023.}
- [2] Remained approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decreased [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.A_1_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No investment in production capacity in 2023 and 2024

3.17.A_2 {capacity investment - speed - ICEV} And how do you expect these investments to change in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increase → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.A_2_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2025, but none in 2024.}
- [2] Remain approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decrease [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.A_2_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No investment in production capacity in 2024 and 2025 (expected)

{Filter: Only for respondents with “3.5 = No [2]” (no innovation) OR Do not know [98]” AND “3.14.a = Yes [1]” (ICE production capacity change) AND “3.14.b = No [2]” (no EV production capacity change). Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.17.A_X Do you expect to undertake investments in the production capacity related to EVs in 2025?

- Yes [1] / No [2]

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR Don’t know [98] OR No response” AND “3.14.b = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.17.B_1 {capacity investment - speed - EV - past} How have your enterprise’s automotive production capacity investments related to EVs changed in 2024 compared to 2023?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increased → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.B_1_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there were investments in 2024, but none in 2023.}
- [2] Remained approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decreased [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.B_1_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No investment in production capacity in 2023 and 2024

3.17.B_2 {capacity investment - speed - EV} And how do you expect these investments to change in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increase → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.B_2_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2025, but none in 2024.}
- [2] Remain approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decrease [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.B_2_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No investment in production capacity in 2024 and 2025 (expected)

{Filter: Only for respondents with “3.5 = No [2]” (no innovation) OR Do not know [98]” AND “3.14.a = No [2]” (no ICE production capacity change) AND “3.14.b = Yes [1]” (EV production capacity change). Skip for respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.17.A_X Do you expect to undertake investments in the production capacity related to ICEVs in 2025?

Yes [1] / No [2]

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.5 = No [2] OR Don’t know [98] OR No response” AND “3.14.b = Yes [1]” AND “3.14.x = [1]”.}

3.17.X_1 {capacity investment - speed - automotive - past} How have your enterprise’s automotive production capacity investments changed in 2024 compared to 2023?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increased → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.X_1_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there were investments in 2024, but none in 2023.}
- [2] Remained approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decreased [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.X_1_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No investment in production capacity in 2023 and 2024

3.17.X_2 {capacity investment - speed - automotive} And how do you expect these investments to change in 2025?

{Alternatively: do not know [98]; prefer not to say [99]}

- [1] Increase → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.X_2_X Ca. ___ %
{INT: Enter “555” if there was an innovation expenditure in 2025, but none in 2024.}
- [2] Remain approximately the same (+/- 5%)
- [3] Decrease [3] → If yes, by approximately what percentage? 3.17.X_2_X Ca. ___ %
- [97] No investment in production capacity in 2024 and 2025 (expected)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14 = Yes [1]”.}

3.18 {production funding} During the past three years 2022 to 2024, did your enterprise receive any public financial support for your automotive production capacity changes?

Please include any public investment support from Germany and the EU.

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

3.18.a For ICEVs: Yes [1] / No [2] {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.a = Yes [1]”.}

3.18.b For EVs: Yes [1] / No [2] {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.b = Yes [1]”.}

3.18.x For Automotive: Yes [1] / No [2] {Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14.x = [1]”.}

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.14 = No [2] OR Don’t Know [98] OR No response [99]”. (i.e. those not changing their automotive production capacity in the past 3 years).}

3.19 {new capacity changers 2025} Does your enterprise plan to undertake any changes in its automotive production capacity in 2025?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

Yes [1] / No [2]

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.19 = Yes [1]”.}

3.20 {new capacity changers 2025 - TECH} In which of the following technological domains are these changes in your enterprise’s automotive production capacity in 2025?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

3.20.a ICEVs: Yes [1] / No [2]

3.20.b EVs: Yes [1] / No [2]

{INT: Do not read aloud! The enterprise may be unable to distinguish between the ICEV and EV domains (e.g. if components are supplied independently of the drive technology and no market distinction is made between the two domains).}

3.20.x Distinction not possible [1]

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.20.a = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.20.x = [1]”.}

3.21.A {capacity adjustments - new 2025 - ICEV} What type of capacity adjustments is your enterprise planning to undertake in 2025 related to ICEVs?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- **3.21.A_1 Modernizing production capacity** (e.g. upgrading or renewing existing ICEV-related buildings, machinery, equipment or IT) [1]
- **3.21.A_2 Expanding production capacity** [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these expansions connected to...
 - **3.18.A_2_1 ... adding new facilities for ICEVs?** [1]
 - **3.18.A_2_2 ...relocating ICEV-related facilities into Germany?** [1]
 (If yes, please specify country of origin: **3.21.A_2_2_X:** ____)
- **3.21.A_3 Reducing production capacity** (e.g. repurposing or closing ICEV-related facilities) [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these reductions connected to...
 - **3.21.A_3_1 ... repurposing facilities?** (e.g. shifting assets and equipment away from ICEV-related production) [1]
 (If yes, please specify new purpose(s): **3.21.A_3_1_X:** ____)
 - **3.21.A_3_2 ... relocating ICEV-related facilities out of Germany?** [1]
 (If yes, please specify destination country **3.21.A_3_2_X:** ____)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.20.b = Yes [1]”. Skip for respondents with “3.20.x = [1]”.}

3.21.B {capacity adjustments - new 2025 - EV} What type of capacity adjustments is your enterprise planning to undertake in 2025 related to EVs?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- **3.21.B_1 Modernizing production capacity** (e.g. upgrading or renewing existing EV-related buildings, machinery, equipment or IT) [1]
- **3.21.B_2 Expanding production capacity** [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these expansions connected to...
 - **3.21.B_2_1 ... adding new facilities for EVs ?** [1]
 - **3.21.B_2_2 ... relocating EV-related facilities into Germany?** [1]
 (If yes, please specify origin country **3.21.B_2_2_X:** ____)
- **3.21.B_3 Reducing production capacity** (e.g. repurposing or closing EV-related facilities) [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these reductions connected to...
 - **3.21.B_3_1 ... repurposing facilities?** (e.g. shifting assets and equipment away from EV-related production) [1]
 (If yes, please specify new purpose(s): **3.21.A=B_3_1_X:** ____)
 - **3.21.B_3_2 ... relocating EV-related facilities out of Germany?** [1]
 (If yes, please specify destination country: **3.21.B_3_2_X:** ____)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.20.x = [1]”.}

3.21.X {capacity adjustments - new 2025 - automotive} What type of capacity adjustments is your enterprise planning to undertake in 2025 related to the automotive industry?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- **3.21.X_1 Modernizing production capacity** (e.g. upgrading or renewing existing buildings, machinery, equipment or IT related to the automotive domain) [1]
- **3.21.X_2 Expanding production capacity** [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these expansions connected to...
 - **3.21.X_2_1 ... adding new automotive facilities?** [1]
 - **3.21.X_2_2 ... relocating automotive facilities into Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify origin country **3.21.X_2_2_X**: ____)
- **3.21.X_3 Reducing production capacity** (e.g. repurposing or closing automotive facilities) [1] → If selected, ask to specify:
Were some of these reductions connected to...
 - **3.21.X_3_1 ... repurposing automotive facilities?** (e.g. shifting assets and equipment away from automotive in the current portfolio) [1]
(If yes, please specify new purpose(s): **3.21.X_3_1_X**: ____)
 - **3.21.X_3_2 ... relocating automotive facilities out of Germany?** [1]
(If yes, please specify destination country: **3.21.X_3_2_X**: ____)

{Filter: Only ask respondents with “3.19 = Yes [1]”.}

3.22 {capacity investments - new 2025} What production capacity investments do you expect for your enterprise in 2025? Please round up to the nearest thousand.

{INT: If unsure, please have the respondent provide an estimate.

{Alternatively: More than 1 billion € [999997]; do not know [999998]; prefer not to say [999999].}

Investments related to...

3.22.a ... ICEVs: approx. ____ thousand € {Filter: only if “3.20.a = [1]”.}

3.22.b ... EVs: approx. ____ thousand € {Filter: only if “3.20.b = [1]”}

3.22.x ... Automotive: approx. ____ thousand € {Filter: only if “3.20.x = [1]”.}

III. D: Global links of your enterprise

We would now like to ask you three questions about your enterprise’s global links regarding your automotive business activities.

3.23 {global - technology} For the past three years 2022 to 2024, please evaluate the importance of technological collaborators from the following countries.

*Please use a scale from 1 (not important at all) to 6 (very important). [1:6]
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}*

{INT: EU= European Union includes: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

EFTA = European Free Trade Association includes: Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland.}

Importance of technological collaborators from...

- 3.23.a ...Germany.
- 3.23.b ...Other EU or EFTA countries.
- 3.23.c ... United Kingdom (UK).
- 3.23.d ... United States (US).
- 3.23.e ... China.
- 3.23.f ... Other countries not listed above.

3.24 {global - supply chain} For the past three years 2022 to 2024, please evaluate the importance of suppliers of raw materials and intermediate goods from the following countries for your enterprise’s automotive business activities.

*Please use a scale from 1 (not important at all) to 6 (very important). [1:6]
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}*

{INT: EU= European Union includes: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

EFTA = European Free Trade Association includes: Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland.}

Importance of suppliers of raw materials and intermediate goods from...

- 3.24.a ... Germany.
- 3.24.b ... other EU or EFTA countries.
- 3.24.c ... United Kingdom (UK).
- 3.24.d ... United States (US).
- 3.24.e ... China.
- 3.24.f ... Other countries not listed above.

3.25 {global - market} For the past three years 2022 to 2024, please evaluate the importance of the following markets for your enterprise’s automotive turnover based on the scale from 1 (not important at all) to 6 (very important).

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

{INT: EU= European Union includes: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

EFTA = European Free Trade Association includes: Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland.}

Importance of automotive turnover from customers located in...

3.25.a ... Germany.

3.25.b ... other EU and EFTA countries.

3.25.c ... United Kingdom (UK).

3.25.d ... United States (US).

3.25.e ... China.

3.25.f ... Other countries not listed above.

IV: ORGANISATIONAL PROFILE: employees, turnover & resources

In the following, we ask for general key figures of your enterprise.

4.1 {employees 2024} What was the average number of persons employed by your enterprise in 2024?

{INT: {In case of queries} Total number of persons (headcount) who work in the enterprise (inclusive of working proprietors, partners working regularly in the unit and unpaid family workers), as well as persons who work outside the enterprise’s premises and are paid by it (e.g., sales representatives, delivery personnel, repair and maintenance teams). It excludes manpower supplied to the enterprise by other enterprises and persons carrying out repair and maintenance work in the enterprise on behalf of other enterprises. Please provide an integer number.}

{Other possible answers: Do not know [99998], No response [99999]}

Ca. _____

4.1_X {Filter: Only ask respondents with “4.1 = Do not know [98] OR keine Angabe [99].”}

Could you instead indicate into which of the following categories your number of employees fell in 2024?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- [1] Less than 15 employees
- [2] Between 15 and 149 employees
- [3] Between 150 and 999 employees
- [4] More than 1000 employees

4.2 {employees 2024 - TECH} And what was the share of the persons employed by your enterprise in 2024 related to the following technological domains?

{INT: Two decimal places are possible. The period functions as the decimal separator. If unsure, please estimate.}

{Other possible answers: Do not know [999998], No response [999999]}

Share in percentage related to...

4.2.a ... ICEVs: ____%

4.2.b ... EVs: ____%

4.3 {turnover 2024} What was your enterprise’s total turnover (incl. exports) in 2024?

Please round up to the nearest thousand.

{INT: Turnover is defined as the market sales of goods and services - include all taxes except VAT.}

{Other possible answers: more than one billion € [999997]; do not know [999998]; prefer not to say [999999]}

Ca. ___ thousand €

4.4 {turnover 2024 - automotive} And what was your turnover related to the automotive industry in 2024?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

{INT: If unsure, please estimate.}

[1] Absolute: approximately ___ thousand Euro

[2] Percentage of total turnover: approximately ____%

{INT: Two decimal places possible. Period functions as decimal separator.}

4.5 {export} And of this, how big was the share of exports?

{INT: If unsure, please estimate. Export means sales out of Germany. Two decimal places are possible.}

{Other possible answers: Do not know [99998], No response [99999]}

Approximately ___ %

4.6 {turnover 2024 - automotive - TECH} Approximately what was the share of your enterprise’s automotive turnover in 2024 related to the following technological domains?

{INT: Two decimal places possible. Period functions as decimal separator. If unsure, please estimate. Does not need to add up to 100%.}

{Other possible answers: Do not know [99998], No response [99999]}

Share of automotive turnover related to...

4.6.a ...ICEVs: Approximately ___ %

4.6.b ...EVs: Aproximately ___ %

4.7 {turnover 2025 - automotive - TECH} And for 2025, do you expect the turnover related to these technological domains to increase, stay the same or decrease?

{INT: Please relate the changes to the absolute turnover in these areas, not the shares.}

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

4.7.a ICEV turnover will ...

- Increase [1]
- Stay about the same (+/- 5%) [2]
- Decrease [3]

4.7.b EV turnover will ...

- Increase [1]
- Stay about the same (+/- 5%) [2]
- Decrease [3]

4.8 {corporate targets} Does your enterprise have any of the following internal targets?

- [1] Climate Neutrality Target → If so, climate neutral by which year? 4.8_X _____
- [2] E-mobility Target
- [3] Circular Economy Target
- [90] No internal target in these areas

4.9 {resources} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements about your enterprise’s current resources.

Please answer using a scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

My enterprise has...

- 4.9.a {human resources} ... the right team with the right expertise.
- 4.9.b {financial resources} ... sufficient financial resources.
- 4.9.c {information resources} ... all relevant data and the best analytical tools.
- 4.9.d {physical resources} ... the necessary infrastructure, equipment and natural resources.
- 4.9.e {network resources} ... good connections with all relevant actors.
- 4.9.f {legitimacy resources} ... a good reputation and trust among external stakeholders.

4.10 {sensing and seizing} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements about your enterprise’s general skills.

Please answer again using the same scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

My enterprise is very good at...

4.10.a {analytical} ... analysing trends, interpreting data and making informed decisions.

4.10.b {operational} ... managing daily operations effectively and getting things done.

4.10.c {coordination} ... building partnerships and working with other organisations.

4.10.d {learning} ... learning from experiences and adjusting our strategy.

4.10.e {policy} ... understanding and accessing available policy support.

4.10.f {political} ... negotiating deals and shaping policy and market environments.

4.11 {transforming} Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements about your enterprise’s R&D and marketing skills.

*Please answer again using the same scale from 1 to 6. 1 means “do not agree at all” and 6 means “fully agree”. [1:6]
{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}*

My enterprise is very good at ...

4.11.a {RD - org learning} ... identifying and learning about promising new technologies.

4.11.b {MK - market foresight} ... assessing the potential of new markets.

4.11.c {RD - strategic orientation} ... developing a long-term vision and strategic roadmap.

4.11.d {RD - capacity building} ... upskilling its employees for new technologies.

4.11.e {MK - marketing} ... developing new advertising or promotion strategies.

V: OUTLOOK: Future political framework conditions

We would like to close by asking about your preferences for future policy changes.

5.1 {German policy preferences} Looking at the new German government and its coalition treaty, please indicate the extent to which your enterprise would prefer the following policy options to support the transformation of the German automotive industry.

Please use a scale from 1 (Not at all preferred) to 6 (Highly preferred). [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

Prioritising public funds...

- 5.1.a ... for tax benefits for EVs (e.g. by cutting benefits for ICEVs)
- 5.1.b ... to support the adoption of EVs by low-income households (e.g. social leasing of EVs)
- 5.1.c ... to support education, research and innovation
- 5.1.d ... to reduce the electricity price for all (e.g., through lowering electricity tax, surcharges and grid fees)
- 5.1.e ... to introduce a cheaper industrial electricity price for energy-intensive industries
- 5.1.f ... to support for the establishment of a domestic battery production (incl. recycling)
- 5.1.g ... to support the build-up of the hydrogen infrastructure for heavy duty vehicles

Please also indicate the extent to which your enterprise would prefer the following policy options to support the transformation of the German automotive industry.

Please continue to answer using a scale from 1 (Not at all preferred) to 6 (Highly preferred).

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- 5.1.h Relaxing CO₂ fleet emission standards (e.g. abandoning penalties for non-compliance)
- 5.1.i Maintaining the 100% zero-emission sales target for new passenger and light duty vehicles starting in 2035 (also referred to as ‘ICEV ban’)
- 5.1.j Avoiding the introduction of an EU-wide electrification quota for company car fleets
- 5.1.k Linking taxes, subsidies and road fees to the CO₂-intensity of vehicles
- 5.1.l Promoting the introduction of EU emission trading 2 for transport and heating (ETS 2)
- 5.1.m Ensuring technology openness in policies and measures (e.g. for e-fuels)
- 5.1.n Regulatory changes enabling autonomous and connected driving
- 5.1.o Policy support for repurposing automotive production capacities for the defense industry
- 5.1.p Others → Please specify: 5.1.p_X: _____

5.2 {International responses} Looking at the EU’s and Germany’s potential policy responses to international EV competition, please indicate how much your enterprise would prefer the following policy options.

Please use a scale from 1 (Not at all preferred) to 6 (Highly preferred). [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

Introducing or increasing...

5.2.a {general - value} ... regulatory requirements for EV products and components sold in the European market (e.g. based on cybersecurity, environmental standards, or labour rights).

5.2.b {general - IP - local content} ... local content requirements for EVs and components made in Europe (e.g. to qualify for support, public procurement or market access).

5.2.c {general - IP - subsidies} ... production subsidies for EVs and components made in Europe.

5.2.d {China - tariffs} ... import tariffs for Chinese EVs entering the European market.

5.2.e {China - standards} ... minimum price requirements for Chinese EVs entering the European market.

5.2.f {China - transfer} ... joint venture or local employment requirements for Chinese enterprises entering the European market.

5.2.g {US - tariffs} ... retaliatory tariffs on US automotive products (e.g., Tesla) entering the European market.

5.2.h {US - relocation} ... policy support to mitigate relocation risks of German firms responding to tariff pressures.

5.2.i {US - free trade} ... negotiations for bilateral or multilateral trade agreements to remove trade restrictions related to EVs (e.g. with US).

5.2.j {others} Others → If applicable: Please specify: 5.2.j_X: _____ {INT: Note open-ended answer.}

5.3 {policy recommendation} Would you like to share any recommendations on how to improve the policy framework conditions for the transformation of the German automotive industry?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

[1] Yes, through: _____

[2] No

5.4 {open} Do you wish to share any other important points for the transformation of the German automotive industry?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

[1] Yes: _____

[2] No

{Filter: Ask only in the Online Version (CAWI).}

5.5 {acceleration challenges} To which extent do you agree with the following statements about the transformation of Germany’s automotive industry?

Please use a scale from 1 (do not agree at all) to 6 (fully agree). [1:6]

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

There are currently big challenges associated with...

5.5.a_1 {WHO_1} ... the limited availability of the charging infrastructure.

5.5.a_2 {WHO_2} ... slow electricity grid upgrades and expansions.

5.5.b_1 {MSI_1} high electricity and/or energy prices.

5.5.b_2 {MSI_2} obstacles to automated and connected driving.

5.5.c_1 {DEC_1} ... the loss of jobs in the automotive industry.

5.5.c_2 {DEC_2} ... shrinking profits of German car manufacturers.

5.5.c_3 {DEC_1} ... rising support for right-wing populist parties.

5.5.d_1 {INT_1} ... strong competition from Chinese manufacturers.

5.5.d_2 {INT_2} ... high geopolitical tensions and trade risks from tariffs.

5.5.e_1 {EXP_1} ... slow mass market uptake of EVs.

5.5.e_2 {EXP_2} ... the shortage of skilled labour.

5.5.e_3 {EXP_3} ... the lack of a common vision for the future of mobility.

5.5.f_1 {JUS_1} ... the limited availability of affordable EVs.

5.5.f_2 {JUS_2} ... the lack of affordable charging solutions in multi-unit housing.

5.5.g_1 {CON_1} ... the limited public acceptance for EVs.

5.5.g_2 {CON_2} ... the strong emotional attachment to ICEVs.

5.5.h_1 {GOV_1} ... the uncertainty of future policy support for EVs.

5.5.h_2 {GOV_2} ... the continuation of tax benefits for ICEVs.

5.5.i_1 {FIN} ... securing long-term finance for climate investments.

5.5.i_2 {SUS} ... increasing costs due to climate change and other environmental risks.

5.5.i_3 {OTH} ... other challenges. → If so, please specify: 5.5.i_3_X: _____ {open text}

5.6 {respondent} Which position do you hold in your enterprise?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

_____ {Record open response}

5.7 {results} Are you interested in receiving the results of the study by email?

{Other possible answers: Do not know [98], No response [99]}

- Yes [1] → Which email address should we send them to? 5.7_X: _____
- No [2]

Many thanks for your responses. They are highly valuable to us.

This brings us to the end of the interview. Thank you very much for your time, your patience, and for answering all of our questions.

Appendix

Focus & Definitions

This survey addresses the transformation of the German automotive industry, with a particular focus on maintaining its competitiveness in a climate-neutral future.

This questionnaire asks for information about your business activities in Germany’s automotive industry, differentiating between two technological domains: Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles (in short: ICEVs) and Electric Vehicles (in short: EVs). We use these terms following the definitions by the European Alternative Fuels Observatory:

Internal Combustion Engine Vehicle (ICEV): *“An Internal Combustion Engine is an engine that generates motive power by burning petrol, oil, or other fuels with air inside the engine. The hot gases produced are used to drive a piston or perform other work as they expand. An ICE vehicle is a vehicle propelled by an internal combustion engine.”*

Electric Vehicle (EV): *“A motor vehicle equipped with a powertrain containing at least one non-peripheral electric machine as an energy converter, along with an electric rechargeable energy storage system that can be recharged externally. The term 'Electric Vehicle' includes Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs), Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs), and Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs).”*

- *Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV): “Battery Electric Vehicle, also known as all-electric or 100% electric vehicle, means an electric vehicle that exclusively runs on the electric motor, with no secondary source of propulsion.”*
- *Fuel cell electric vehicle (FCEV): “Vehicle which uses a fuel cell to power its on-board electric motor, generally using oxygen from the air and compressed hydrogen. A fuel cell electric vehicle that is fueled with hydrogen emits only water and heat.”*
- *Plug-in hybrid electric vehicle (PHEV): “Means an electric vehicle constituted by a conventional combustion engine combined with an electric propulsion system, which can be recharged from an external electric power source”*